

1 **Title: Production of omega 3-rich oils from underutilized chia seeds. Comparison between**
2 **supercritical fluid and pressurized liquid extraction methods**

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29 *Author contribution to the article*

30 The authors' responsibilities were following:

31 **DVB:** Responsible for the current analyses by SFE and participate in the writing of the
32 manuscript;

33 **MVC:** Responsible for the current analyses by PLE and participate in the writing of the
34 manuscript;

35 **PCG:** Initiated the current analyses and supplied valuable knowledge and scientific consultation
36 during the process

37 **TF:** Took part in the funding and design of experiments and participate in the writing of the
38 manuscript;

39 **JF:** Took part in the funding and design of experiments and participate in the writing of the
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42 *Statement of author contributions*

43 The authors have all contributed to this manuscript read and approved this final submission.

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51

52 **Abstract**

53 Chia seeds constitute a promising source of α -linolenic acid (ALA). In the present work, an
54 underutilized and cheaper set of chia seeds, which were discarded after the harvest according to
55 quality criteria - named in this work as low oil content seeds (LOCS) - have been evaluated as a
56 potential source for obtaining PUFA-enriched oils against the commonly studied high-quality
57 chia seeds denoted as high oil content seeds (HOCS) in this study. Two efficient and
58 environmental friendly techniques, supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) and pressurized liquid
59 extraction (PLE), were evaluated to optimize the extraction process of chia oil. At 60°C, by
60 using pressurized food-grade ethanol, recoveries close to 100% were achieved from both sets of
61 seeds in a short extraction time (10 min). By using SFE, the greatest oil extraction yield (>95%)
62 was attained at the highest pressure and temperature conditions (45 MPa and 60°C) after 240
63 min. At the early stage of SFE extraction, both LOCS and HOCS exhibited a similar kinetic
64 behavior, reaching oil extraction rates of 0.59 g oil/min and 0.64 g oil/min, respectively. No
65 differences were found between the fatty acid profile of the oils extracted from LOCS and
66 HOCS both by PLE and SFE. The linolenic (ALA) and linoleic acid (LA) concentrations ranged
67 between 65-68% and 17-23% respectively, and a predominance of high molecular weight
68 triglycerides (\geq CN50), was found in all extracted oils. In conclusion, LOCS might constitute a
69 new suitable raw material for the production of ALA-enriched oils. Concerning the extraction
70 methods assayed, the oil was almost entirely recovered by both PLE and SFE at the used
71 conditions.

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73 **Keywords:**

74 Chia seed; α -linolenic acid (ALA); supercritical fluid extraction (SFE); pressurized liquid
75 extraction (PLE); triacylglycerol composition; FAME composition

77 1. Introduction

78

79 Currently there is a constant search of natural ingredients whose intake provides benefits for
80 health. One of the most promising sources is chia seeds, which are gaining an immense
81 importance as a new raw material to obtain beneficial, nutritional food ingredients. Chia (*Salvia*
82 *hispanica* L.) is a plant of the *Lamiaceae* family native to Mexico and Guatemala. Due to its
83 health properties, the seeds have been traditionally used as a food and applied in herbal
84 medicine. Recently a number of studies have been carried out to obtain chia compounds for the
85 food industry in order to improve food formulations (Capitani, Nolasco, & Tomas, 2016;
86 Coorey, Tjoe, & Jayasena, 2014; Julio et al., 2016; Olivos-Lugo, Valdivia-Lopez, & Tecante,
87 2010) and for the production of functional foods, due to the significant amount of bioactive
88 ingredients contained in these seeds, such as dietary fibre and phenolic compounds (Oliveira-
89 Alves et al., 2017; Reyes-Caudillo, Tecante, & Valdivia-López, 2008). Additionally, chia seeds
90 contain a large amount of oil (20-35% mass of dry seed), which is rich in polyunsaturated fatty
91 acids (PUFA), especially in linoleic acid (LA) (15-20% of total fatty acids) and ω -3 α -linolenic
92 acid (ALA) (60-65%) (Porrás-Loaiza, Jiménez-Munguía, Sosa-Morales, Palou, & Lopez-Malo,
93 2014). LA and ALA are considered essential to health and because the human body is unable to
94 synthesize them, they are highly demanded ingredients within the food and cosmetic industrial
95 sectors.

96 Several solvents and extraction techniques have been studied to obtain oil from chia seeds.
97 Ixtaina et al. (2010) studied the effect of temperature, pressure and time on the supercritical CO₂
98 (SCCO₂) extraction of oil from a Mexican chia variety. Authors obtained an oil recovery of
99 92.8%, at 45 MPa, 80°C and 300 min. In another contribution (Ixtaina et al. 2011) the authors
100 obtained oil recoveries which ranged from 82% (25 MPa, 40°C and 285 min) to 97% (45 MPa,
101 60°C and 138 min) from an Argentinian seed variety. Rocha Uribe, Novelo Pérez, Castillo
102 Kaul, Rosado Rubio & Alcocer (2011) evaluated oil extraction using the same temperatures,
103 but lower pressures (13.6-40.8 MPa) and the extractions were carried out in a combined static-
104 dynamic mode. The highest extraction yield (7.2%, expressed as mass of oil extracted/mass of

105 seeds) was obtained at the highest pressure and temperature and after 40 minutes of extraction
106 time, but these operational conditions were not sufficient to remove the entire amount of oil.
107 Guindani et al. (2016) evaluated the oil extraction from chia seed cakes using SCCO₂ with
108 ethanol and ethyl acetate as co-solvents. The highest extraction yield (10.6%) with pure CO₂
109 was obtained at 30 MPa and 50°C. The use of co-solvents (2.5% mass) produced an appreciable
110 increase in the extraction yield, especially with ethanol. With regards to the use of organic
111 liquid solvents, de Mello, dos Santos García & da Silva (2015) studied the ultrasound-assisted
112 extraction of oil, achieving extraction yields up to 27.2% by using ethyl acetate as a solvent.
113 Tolentino et al. (2014), Segura-Campos, Ciau-Solís, Rosado-Rubio, Chel-Guerrero & Betancur-
114 Ancona (2014) and Amato et al. (2015) extracted the chia seeds oil using the IUPAC Soxhlet
115 procedure (IUPAC, 1992) with conventional organic solvents, such as petroleum ether or
116 hexane. Zanqui et al. (2015) evaluated the subcritical extraction of oil with propane and
117 Castejón, Luna & Señorans (2017) the oil extraction by PLE, using hexane, ethyl acetate and
118 aqueous ethanol as solvents. Dabrowski, Konopka, Czaplicki & Tanska (2017) evaluated the
119 influence of three techniques, the traditional Soxhlet extraction with hexane and acetone, the
120 SCCO₂ extraction and the use of cold- and hot-pressing methods. In all these studies,
121 independent of what extraction technique and solvents applied, the amount of ALA and LA in
122 the extracts was approximately 60-65% and 20-25% of total fatty acids, respectively.
123 In recent years, the interest in chia seeds as an alternative source of polyunsaturated oil has risen
124 considerably. Post-harvest the chia seeds are cleaned, classified and selected to be marketed
125 meanwhile those damaged or partially broken are separated and underutilized. Although this
126 damaged by-product can be used for animal feed, its potential as a source of enriched PUFA oil
127 has not been explored until now. Additionally, its low price due to the market surplus, along
128 with its notable oil content would make these underutilized low-quality seeds a material worthy
129 of consideration for the food industry.
130 In this work, the extraction performance and the composition of oils obtained from two different
131 batches of Mexican chia seeds, high oil content seeds (HOCS) and underutilized or low oil
132 content seeds (LOCS), have been assessed for the first time. The aim of the present work is to

133 evaluate the suitability of LOCS to be used as a raw material for the efficient production of
134 PUFA enriched oils containing high concentrations of ALA. For this purpose, two efficient and
135 green technologies, SFE and PLE, were evaluated to optimize the operational conditions to
136 recover the totality of oil contained in the seeds.

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138 **2. Materials and methods**

139 **2.1 Sample and reagents**

140 **2.1.1 Sample preparation**

141 Chia seeds (*Salvia hispanica* L.) from Mexico were generously supplied by Hector Di Luca
142 (Primaria Premium Raw Materials, S.L). Samples denoted as HOCS and LOCS, correspond
143 respectively, to high and low oil content chia seeds. The oil content (value provided by the
144 supplier) contained in each batch of chia seeds was 25.2% (HOCS) and 20.6% (LOCS) on a dry
145 basis. Clean seeds were ground in a knife mill cooled by liquid nitrogen and were sieved in an
146 electromagnetic, digital sieve shaker using mesh sieves, stainless steel with 200 mm diameter,
147 (CISA Cedaceria Industrial S.L. Barcelona, Spain) to obtain a particle size ranging from 250 µm
148 to 500 µm. Samples were kept at 20°C until their use.

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150 **2.1.2 Chemicals**

151 All solvents were HPLC grade, and MS grade when available. Dichloromethane, hexane,
152 dimethylformamide, sulphuric acid 98%, methanol and acetonitrile were purchased from
153 Labscan (Dublin, Ireland) and food grade ethanol 96%, v/v (F.C.C.) for PLE was obtained from
154 Alcoholes Montplet (Barcelona, Spain). Absolute ethanol ≥98.5%, employed for SFE, sea sand
155 used as dispersant, sodium sulphate anhydrous and sodium carbonate were obtained from
156 Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Sodium methoxide 95%, the TAG standards trinainoin and
157 tridecanoin, and the FFA standards, were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).
158 Reference samples with known composition, butterfat BCR-164 and BCR-519 (EU
159 Commissions; Brussels, Belgium) were from Fedelco Inc. (Madrid, Spain).

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161 **2.2 Pressurized liquid extraction**

162 Pressurized liquid extractions (PLE) were carried out in an Accelerated Solid Extraction ASE-
163 200 equipment (Dionex Corp., Sunnyvale, CA), using dichloromethane/methanol (D:M)
164 solution (2:1, v/v) and food grade ethanol (EtOH) as extraction solvents. A detailed description
165 of the extraction procedure and equipment employed can be found in the works reported by
166 Castro-Gómez et al. (2014) and Castro-Gómez, Montero & Fontecha (2017).
167 Experimental conditions were the same for both solvents. Briefly, 2 g of chia seeds sample were
168 mixed with 2 g of sea sand, which was used as a dispersant, and loaded into a stainless-steel
169 extraction cell covered with filters on both sides. The extraction was done during one static
170 cycle of 10 min at a pressure of 10.3 MPa. Three different temperatures (40 C, 60 C and 80 °C)
171 were assayed. The oil extracts obtained were concentrated by removing the organic solvent in a
172 rotary vacuum evaporator (Strike 202 model; Steroglass S.R.L., Perugia, Italy). In the case of
173 ethanol, to remove all traces of water, the liquid extracts were previously filtered through a
174 Whatman 1-phase separator filter paper (Whatman, Maidstone, UK) fitted with a vacuum pump
175 and containing approximately 3 g of sodium sulphate anhydrous. Finally, all oil extracts were
176 fully evaporated under a gentle stream of nitrogen, weighed, stored in amber vials, and frozen at
177 -35°C until analysis. Each extraction was performed in triplicate.

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179 **2.3 Supercritical fluid extraction**

180 Supercritical fluid extractions were carried out using a pilot-plant supercritical fluid extractor
181 (model SF2000; Thar Technology, Pittsburgh, PA, USA), comprising a 0.273 L cylinder
182 extraction cell and two separators (S1 and S2), each of 0.5 L capacity, with independent control
183 of temperature and pressure. A detailed description of the equipment can be found in the work
184 reported by Villanueva-Bermejo, Zahran, Rodríguez-Risco, Reglero & Fornari (2017).
185 A kinetic study was performed using both types of chia seeds. Extractions from LOCS were
186 carried out at two pressures (25 and 45 MPa), two temperatures (40 and 60°C), 40 g/min of CO₂
187 flow rate and 240 min extraction time. Pressure conditions were selected considering the
188 increased solubility of oil seeds in SCCO₂ at high CO₂ densities. At these conditions, densities

189 of SCCO₂ varied from 786.6 kg/m³ (25 MPa and 60°C) to 974.7 kg/m³ (45 MPa and 40°C)
190 (NIST Chemistry WebBook, 2018). In the case of temperature, values higher than 60°C were
191 discarded in order to avoid the thermal degradation of the oil.

192 After that, 45 MPa and 40°C were selected in terms of oil yield and fatty acid composition as
193 the best pressure and temperature to optimize the oil extraction of HOCS. In this sense, several
194 CO₂ flow rates (27, 40 and 54 g/min, which represent a CO₂-to-seeds ratio of 50, 70 and 100,
195 respectively) were studied and the extraction time was set to 240 min. The mass of chia seeds
196 employed for the experiments was 130 g for all runs. All extracts were obtained by
197 depressurization at the system recirculation pressure (5 MPa). The oil mass obtained in each
198 extraction was collected from both separators and mixed in a single fraction. Afterwards, each
199 SFE extract was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂, filtered through a 0.45 µm Millipore filter coupled to a
200 syringe containing approx. 1 g of anhydrous sodium sulphate and was stored at -35°C until
201 chromatographic analysis.

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203 **2.4 Chemical analysis**

204 **2.4.1 Fatty acid composition**

205 The lipid extracts from chia seeds were derivatized following the method described in Castro-
206 Gómez, Fontecha & Rodríguez-Alcalá (2014). Fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) were
207 separated using a CP-Sil 88 fused-silica capillary column (100 m × 0.25 mm ID, 0.2 µm;
208 Chrompack, Middelburg, The Netherlands) in an Agilent chromatograph (model 6890N;
209 Agilent Technologies Inc., Palo Alto, USA) equipped with an MS detector (Agilent 5973N).
210 Chromatographic conditions were as follows: the column was held at 100°C for 1 min after
211 injection and then temperature increased 7°C/min up to 170°C, held there for 55 min, then
212 increased at 10°C/min up to 230°C and held for 33 min. Total time for chromatographic run was
213 105 min. The injector temperature was set at 250°C. Helium was used as the carrier gas with a
214 column inlet pressure of 0.2 MPa. The injection volume was 1 µL and a split ratio 1:25 was
215 used. MS detector conditions were as follows: transfer line temperature 250°C, source

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216 temperature 230°C, and quadrupole temperature 150°C. The mass spectrometer operated under
217 electron impact mode (70 eV), it was used in total ion current (TIC) mode and scanned the mass
218 range from 40 to 500 m/z. For peak identification, mass spectra obtained in our analysis were
219 compared with those in the National Institute of Standards and Technology library (NIST, 2.1.0
220 version; Gaithersburg, MD, USA). For qualitative and quantitative analysis, response factors
221 were calculated using anhydrous milk fat (reference material BCR-164). Tritridecanoine
222 (C13:0-TAG) was used as an internal standard (200 µL; 1.3 mg/mL) and added to lipid extracts
223 before methylation.

224 **2.4.2 Triacylglycerols composition**

225 For triacylglycerols (TAG) analysis, the oil samples from chia seeds were injected (0.5 µL at 30
226 mg/mL) using a split ratio 1:20 in a CLARUS 400 gas chromatograph (Perkin Elmer Ltd.,
227 Beaconsfield, UK) equipped with an automatic split/splitless injector and a flame ionization
228 detector (FID). A RTX-65TAG fused silica capillary column Crossbond™ (30 m × 0.25 mm
229 ID; 0.1µm film thickness; Restek Corp., Bellefonte, PA, USA) was used. The analysis of TAG
230 groups by different carbon number (CN) content was based on the method described by
231 Fontecha, Mayo, Toledano & Juarez (2006). The temperature program was as follows: the
232 column was held at 120°C for 30 s, then temperature increased 10°C/min up to 220°C, held
233 there for 30 s, then increased at 6°C/min up to 350°C and held for 30 min. Total run time was
234 62.5 min. Injector and FID temperatures were 355°C and 370°C, respectively. Helium (35
235 mL/min) was used as the carrier gas at 0.2 MPa. For TAG determination and quantification, the
236 reference butterfat BCR-519 of known composition was used and glyceryl trinanoate (100 µL; 1
237 mg/mL) was added as internal standard to the lipids extracts before the chromatographic
238 analysis.

240 **3. Results and discussion**

241 **3.1 Pressurized liquid extraction**

242 As can be observed in Figure 1a, a higher oil extraction yield (g of oil/100 g of seeds) was
243 obtained with D:M as temperature increased. Nevertheless, there were no significant differences

244 among 60°C and 80°C as the extraction yields achieved were 19.9% and 19.6%, respectively.
245 When food-grade EtOH was used as solvent, the highest oil extraction yield (17.7%) was also
246 obtained at 60°C and an increase in the extraction temperature did not lead to an enhancement in
247 the amount of oil extracted. Based on this, 60°C was selected as optimal. This effect with
248 regards to applying mild temperatures on the extraction of oil was also observed by Zanqui et al.
249 (2015), who assayed temperatures between 30 and 60°C and obtained the highest chia seeds oil
250 recovery (93.2%) at 45°C and 10 MPa by using *n*-propane. The extraction yield obtained with
251 EtOH was comparable to that reached using D:M and with the added advantage of being a green
252 solvent, unlike D:M, which is a pollutant and toxic mixture.
253 Considering that the amount of oil contained in HOCS and LOCS seeds was 25.2% and 20.6%,
254 respectively, on a dry basis (data provided by the supplier), and considering the extraction yield
255 values (see Figure 1b), the total removal of the oil was practically accomplished for both seed
256 batches. The oil recovery (g of oil extracted/100 g of oil in seeds) for LOCS, was slightly lower
257 when using EtOH (85.9%) than when using D:M (96.6%), while for HOCS, the entire oil (100%
258 recovery) was extracted in just 10 min extraction time and independently of the solvent used.
259 Therefore, EtOH demonstrated to be as efficient as D:M, whose efficacy for the extraction of oil
260 has already been thoroughly corroborated in other studies (Araujo et al., 2013; Iverson, Lang, &
261 Cooper, 2001). Furthermore, the use of a moderate temperature (60°C) allows unsaturated fatty
262 acids to be protected from degradation.

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264 **3.2 Supercritical fluid extraction**

265 The oil extraction kinetic of LOCS (low oil content seeds) was obtained at two pressures (25
266 and 45 MPa) and two temperatures (40 and 60°C). Figure 2 represents the extraction curves of
267 oil from this type of seeds, obtained by SCCO₂ at the different operational conditions. As can be
268 observed, the oil extraction yield increased with the pressure and temperature. The same
269 behaviour has been reported for the SFE of oil from chia seeds containing high amounts of oil
270 (Ixtaina et al. 2011; Ixtaina et al. 2010; Rocha Uribe et al. 2011). When studied by Ixtaina et al.
271 (2011 and 2010), the known crossover effect was not produced at the conditions applied.

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272 However, the same effect observed in the present work was reported by Rocha Uribe et al.
273 (2011) at very similar pressures (27.2 and 40.8 MPa) and same temperatures (40 and 60°C).
274 Nevertheless, additional experiments should be applied to corroborate this behaviour.
275 The highest oil recovery (g of oil extracted/g of oil in seeds) was obtained at 45 MPa and 60°C
276 (90.3% oil recovery), while testing at 25 MPa and 40°C led to the lowest amount of oil extracted
277 (64.5%). Considering the influence of the mass of CO₂/mass of seeds ratio employed on yield,
278 an estimated oil recovery of 85% was obtained at 38 g/g in this work, which is considerably
279 higher than reported by Ixtaina et al. (2010) (40.3%), and lower than obtained experimentally
280 under the same conditions (45 MPa, 60°C and 38 g/g ratio) by the same authors, in another
281 contribution (97% recovery) (Ixtaina et al. 2011), however, they were using high oil content
282 seeds at that time. With regards to the kinetics of the extraction, the highest oil extraction rate at
283 the early extraction stage (fast extraction period mainly controlled by the solubility of oil in
284 CO₂) was also achieved at the maximum pressure and temperature, due to the higher density
285 produced when pressure rises and the increase in the vapour pressure of the solutes at high
286 temperatures. The results show that the mass of oil extracted over time ranged from 0.14 g/min
287 (25 MPa and 60°C) to 0.64 g/min (45 MPa and 60°C).
288 Considering that higher oil recoveries were achieved at 45 MPa (Figure 2) and higher
289 concentrations of ALA were obtained at 40°C (section 3.3) from LOCS, the same pressure and
290 temperature were selected to study the oil extraction from HOCS (higher oil content seeds). To
291 optimize the extraction process and remove all the oil contained in the seeds, the influence of
292 different CO₂ flow rates on the chia oil extraction yield was evaluated for the first time: 27
293 g/min (50 g/g CO₂-to-chia seeds ratio); 40 g/min (74 g/g) and 54 g/min (100 g/g). Figure 3a
294 shows the extraction kinetics plotted as a function of time. As can be observed under these
295 conditions all the oil was extracted (recoveries between 98.5-100%). The extraction rate
296 increased with the flow of CO₂ at the early extraction stage (fast extraction period), at this point,
297 the mass of oil extracted was 0.44 g/min; 0.59 g/min and 0.76 g/min when 27 g/min, 40 g/min
298 and 54 g/min of CO₂ flows were applied, respectively. The value obtained at 40 g/min (0.59 g of
299 oil/min) from HOCS was very close to that obtained with the same conditions (45 MPa, 40°C

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300 and 40 g/min) from LOCS (0.64 g of oil/kg CO₂), therefore, these lower oil content seeds show
301 a kinetic behaviour with the SFE of oil like those obtained for HOCS.
302 Figure 3b shows the recovery of oil plotted as a function of the mass of CO₂/mass of chia seeds
303 ratio used. Based on the amount of oil extracted in the initial fast extraction period, the apparent
304 solubility of chia oil in the SCCO₂ determined at this pressure and temperature was 14.1 g oil/kg
305 CO₂ (the correlation coefficient value was R²=0.984). Although more experiments are necessary
306 to corroborate this value, it was like that obtained at 45 MPa and 40°C with the LOCS (11.1 g
307 oil/kg). Therefore, a similar trend in terms of kinetic and solubility behaviour were observed for
308 both seed batches. Furthermore, the difference in the amount of oil contained in each variety is
309 only 4.6% (the concentration of oil in the HOCS and LOCS is 25.2% and 20.6%, respectively),
310 therefore the LOCS has enough potential to be used as a raw material for the obtaining of high
311 yields of polyunsaturated oil.

312

313 **3.3 Fatty acid and triacylglycerols composition**

314 The oils obtained by PLE and SFE were analysed to determine their composition in fatty acids
315 and Figure 4 shows comparatively the chromatographic profile obtained for each type of chia
316 seeds. With respect to oils extracted from LOCS by PLE at 40, 60 and 80°C (data not shown),
317 ALA concentrations between 64.2-65.7% were achieved and the n-6/n-3 and of the unsaturated-
318 to-saturated fatty acid (UFA/SFA) ratios ranged between 0.27-0.29 and 7.8-8.8, respectively.
319 Therefore, independently of the organic solvent employed the extraction temperature did not
320 have an influence on the oil fatty acid composition.

321 Table 1 shows the main fatty acids present in the oils extracted from the different types of seeds
322 by PLE at 60°C using EtOH and D:M. As can be observed, within each chia seeds variety, the
323 lipid profile obtained with both solvents was very similar. ALA was the major fatty acid in all
324 oil extracts, followed by LA, palmitic, oleic and stearic acids, thus confirming that chia oil is
325 very rich in PUFA (~ 83%).

326 These findings agree with those reported in previous studies on chia seeds (Zanqui et al. 2015;
327 De Mello et al. 2015; Dabrowski et al. 2017), in which other solvents, extraction techniques and

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328 experimental conditions were applied. Zanqui et al. (2015) achieved ALA concentrations of
329 $\approx 61\%$ and an $n-6/n-3 \approx 0.3$ by using subcritical *n*-propane as a solvent. De Mello et al. (2015)
330 used ultrasound-assisted extraction with ethyl acetate to obtain an oil containing 63% of ALA
331 and having an $n-6/n-3$ of 0.31, while Dabrowski et al., (2017) obtained oils having 60-62% of
332 ALA, 12-13% of SFA and $n-6/n-3$ ranged between 0.32-0.35 by cold and hot pressing, as well
333 as by Soxhlet extraction with hexane and acetone. HOCS exhibited a slightly higher value of
334 UFA/SFA ratio as compared to LOCS (Table 1), which is related to the greater presence of
335 ALA and the lower concentration of palmitic acid in the former. Furthermore, the simultaneous
336 decrease of LA levels resulted in lower $n-6/n-3$ ratios (0.25-0.24 for HOCS and 0.29-0.27 for
337 LOCS).

338 Table 2 summarizes the fatty acid composition of oils extracted by SFE from LOCS (at the
339 different operational conditions assayed), as well as from the HOCS (45 MPa, 40°C and 40
340 g/min CO₂ flow rate). As can be observed, an increase in pressure from 25 MPa to 45 MPa at a
341 fixed temperature seemed to exert no effect on the lipid composition of LOCS. Nevertheless,
342 under isobaric conditions, marked differences could be found as the extraction temperature rose.
343 Resulting in a decrease in the amount of ALA observed between both 25 and 45 MPa, with its
344 concentration at 60°C significantly lower ($\sim 55\%$) than that obtained at 40°C ($\sim 67\%$), while the
345 concentration of the remaining fatty acids (particularly LA) increased. Considering that oils are
346 complex mixtures of different lipid classes (fatty acids, mono-, di-, and triglycerides, and fatty
347 acid esters), the intermolecular interactions among them could lead to deviations from pure-
348 component solubility behaviour (Güçlü-Üstündag & Temelli 2000). So, it could be possible that
349 ALA exhibited retrograde solubility behaviour under the experimental conditions studied, while
350 the solubility of the rest of fatty acids or the oil as a whole increased as the temperature rose.

351 When comparing the lipid profiles of the oils from both seed batches, extracted under identical
352 experimental conditions (45 MPa and 40°C), the concentration of ALA found in LOCS
353 (66.25%) was higher than the observed in HOCS oil (59.17%). In addition, the UFA/SFA was
354 higher (9.20 vs 8.38) and the $n-6/n-3$ ratio was more favourable (0.27 vs 0.36) in the case of
355 LOCS.

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356 When seeds from HOCS were extracted by SFE at 45 MPa, 40°C and different CO₂ flow rates,
357 the oil composition was quite similar for all experimental conditions assayed (data not shown).
358 In this case, the n-6/n-3 ratio ranged between 0.34-0.38 and the concentration of ALA, SFA and
359 PUFA was between 58.7-60.4%; 11.3-11.9% and 80.8-81.5%, respectively.
360 Comparing both extraction methods (PLE and SFE), the oil composition and the concentration
361 of the main fatty acids obtained by SFE at 40 °C (Table 2) was almost identical to those
362 obtained by PLE in the case of LOCS (Table 1). Therefore, both extraction technologies are
363 suitable to produce high-quality oils from these seeds. On the contrary, at 60°C the
364 concentration of LA was 27-30% higher in the supercritical extracts, at that expense of ALA,
365 where concentration was around 15% lower than in PLE. The results obtained by SFE in this
366 work with LOCS were very similar to those reported in other studies carried out with SCCO₂
367 and high oil content seeds. Ixtaina et al. (2011) achieved concentrations of ALA around 65%
368 and a value for an n-6/n-3 close to 0.3, at the same pressures and temperatures that were applied
369 in the present work. Likewise, Rocha Uribe et al. (2011) found similar concentrations of ALA
370 (63-66%) and LA (17-18%) in oils which were extracted at pressures higher than 40 MPa, while
371 Dabrowski et al. (2017) reported concentrations between 61-63% and 21-29%, respectively, at
372 28 MPa and higher temperatures (70 and 90°C) than applied in the present study. Therefore, the
373 oils obtained in this work from LOCS by means of these two green extraction technologies
374 (PLE and SFE) exhibited a similar or even a healthier fatty acid profile than that found in
375 HOCS.
376 With respect to the TAG molecular species, the profile obtained in PLE extracts from LOCS at
377 the three temperatures explored (40, 60 and 80°C) with both solvents (D:M and EtOH) was were
378 very similar, as well as those obtained by SFE from HOCS at different CO₂ flow ratios (data not
379 shown). Table 3 presents the TAG composition obtained from both seed varieties by PLE at
380 60°C and by SFE at the different pressures and temperatures and a flow rate of 40 g/min CO₂. In
381 results shown, a predominance of TAG with high molecular weight was observed in all the
382 samples, with CN54 being the most abundant molecular species, in agreement with the high
383 concentration of C18 fatty acids (mono- and polyunsaturated) present in all extracts analysed

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(Table 2). There is also a noticeable presence of the CN52 molecular species, which probably corresponds to those TAGs having palmitic acid esterified to the glycerol backbone. This distribution is in good agreement with TAG composition previously reported for chia seeds oil from different geographical zones (Ixtaina et al. 2011; Timilsena, Vongsvivut, Adhikari, & Adhikar, 2017). These authors, using HPLC/APCI-MS and reverse phase HPLC, respectively, identified twelve TAG molecular species, with trilinolenin ($\alpha\text{Ln}\alpha\text{Ln}\alpha\text{Ln}$) as the major compound. The presence of TAG molecular species with <CN50 in the isolated extracts could be explained by the co-elution of other lipid classes such as diacylglycerols, monoacylglycerols and polar lipids with these TAGs, as described by Castro-Gómez, Montero & Fontecha (2017). Its concentration in PLE extracts (~ 7.8%) was higher than in SFE oils (~ 3.8%) in the case of LOCS, likely due to the use of organic solvents which extract polar compounds more efficiently than SCCO_2 .

On the contrary, the concentration of CN54 was slightly higher in SFE extracts for both seeds oil varieties. This can be explained by the fact that CO_2 is classified as a non-polar solvent, and hence is selective for non-polar solutes such as the TAG. Besides, it is known that TAGs with higher unsaturation degree dissolve better in supercritical carbon dioxide than TAGs with lower unsaturation (Davarnajad, Kassim, Zainal, & Sata, 2008). Comparable results were reported by Jokić et al. (2010), who found a higher content of TAG with unsaturated fatty acids (LA and ALA) in soybean oil obtained by supercritical CO_2 compared to the lipid extracts obtained using organic solvents.

Even though oils obtained from both types of seeds had, overall, a similar TAG composition, the concentration of CN54 was greater in HOCS oils, especially in the case of SFE extracts. In this regard, the content of this TAG molecular species in the oil obtained at 45 MPa and 40°C from LOCS was 15% lower than in oil collected from HOCS, under the same experimental conditions. In the case of the different CO_2 flow rates experimented on HOCS, the increment in the CO_2 /seeds ratio did not produce any effect on the TAG composition of oils.

412 4. Conclusions

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2 413 In this work, two batches of chia seeds with different oil content (LOCS vs. HOCS) were
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4 414 compared for their oil extraction yield as well as their lipid composition, by using two
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6 415 environment-friendly techniques (SFE and PLE). At 60°C, pressurized food-grade ethanol
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8 416 allowed to achieve oil recoveries close to 100% in 10 min for both seed types. By SFE, the
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10 417 greatest oil extraction yield was attained under the highest pressure and temperature conditions
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12 418 tested (45 MPa and 60°C) after 150 min. A similar kinetic behavior, in terms of oil extracted,
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14 419 was observed at the early stage period for HOCS and LOCS, whose oil extraction rates were
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16 420 0.59 g oil/min and 0.64 g/min, respectively.

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19 421 Regarding the fatty acid profile, no noticeable differences were found between the oils extracted
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21 422 from LOCS and HOCS both by PLE and SFE. The main compound in all extracts was ALA
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23 423 which concentration ranged between 65-68%, except for SFE (45MPa, 60 °C). LA was also
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25 424 present in high concentrations 17-23%. A predominance of TAG molecular species \geq CN50,
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27 425 was found in the oils from both HOCS and LOCS, which agrees with the abundance of C18
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29 426 fatty acids (in particular, LA and ALA) in the extracts. This circumstance would explain the
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31 427 greater amount of the CN54TAG in the oils obtained by SFE, given the greater solubility of
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33 428 unsaturated TAGs in supercritical CO₂.

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36 429 In conclusion, LOCS could be efficiently employed for the high-yield production of ALA-
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38 430 enriched oils with a fatty acid composition almost identical to that found in HOCS. Under
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40 431 experimental conditions described in this study, the oil was almost entirely recovered by both
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42 432 PLE and SFE and the quality of the oils obtained was similar as regards their fatty acid
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(a)

(b)

Figure

Figure

(a)

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Figure

1 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

2

3 **Figure 1.** Oil extraction from chia seeds by PLE using ethanol (EtOH) and dichloromethane/
4 methanol (D:M). (a) Oil extraction yield ($\frac{\text{g of oil}}{\text{g of seeds}} \times 100$) obtained at 40, 60 and 80°C from
5 LOCS. (b) Oil extraction yield obtained at 60°C from HOCS and LOCS.

6

7 **Figure 2.** Overall chia oil recovery curves ($\frac{\text{mass of oil extracted}}{\text{mass of oil in seeds}} \times 100$) obtained by SCCO₂ from
8 LOCS, at 25 MPa and 45 MPa, 40°C and 60°C, and 240 min extraction time.

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10 **Figure 3.** Overall chia oil recovery curves ($\frac{\text{mass of oil extracted}}{\text{mass of oil in seeds}} \times 100$) obtained by SCCO₂ from
11 HOCS, at 45 MPa, 40°C and 240 min extraction time. (a) Recovery (%) as a function of the
12 extraction time. (b) Recovery (%) as a function of the mass of CO₂/mass of chia seeds ratio.
13 *Extraction carried out by duplicate (the result is plotted as the mean of both extractions.
14 Average relative standard deviation (ARSD) = $\frac{1}{N} \sum \frac{SD_i}{\bar{x}_i} = 6.2\%$.

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16 **Figure 4.** Comparison of FA profiles, obtained by GC/MS, of the oils extracted from LOCS and
17 HOCS. Experimental conditions: Oil extraction by SFE (45 MPa, 40°C, 240 min) from LOCS
18 (a) and HOCS (b). Oil extraction by PLE (EtOH, 60°C) from chia seeds LOCS (c) and HOCS
19 (d).

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1 TABLES

2

3 **Table 1.** Fatty acid composition (% of total fatty acids) of oils obtained by PLE at 60°C with
 4 dichloromethane/methanol (2:1) (D:M) and ethanol (EtOH) from LOCS and HOCS.

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Fatty acid (%)	LOCS		HOCS	
	D:M	EtOH	D:M	EtOH
C16:0	7.59	7.21	6.43	6.28
C18:0	2.78	2.63	2.50	2.43
C18:1 <i>cis</i> 9	5.74	5.58	5.04	4.95
C18:2 (<i>cis</i> 9, 12)	18.40	17.71	16.83	16.67
C18:3 (<i>cis</i> 9, 12, 15)	64.22	65.69	68.26	68.84
SFA	10.81	10.21	9.17	8.89
MUFA	6.57	6.39	5.74	5.59
PUFA	82.63	83.39	85.09	85.52
UFA	89.20	89.78	90.83	91.11
n-6/n-3	0.29	0.27	0.25	0.24
UFA/SFA	8.26	8.79	9.90	10.25

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11 **Table 2.** Fatty acid composition (% of total fatty acids) of oils extracted by SFE from LOCS
 12 (25-45 MPa, 40°C- 60°C) and HOCS (45 MPa and 40°C). Extraction time: 240 min; CO₂ flow
 13 rate: 40 g/min.

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Fatty acid (%)	LOCS				HOCS
	25 MPa		45 MPa		45 MPa
	40°C	60°C	40°C	60°C	40°C
C16:0	6.34	8.60	6.87	8.41	7.57
C18:0	2.64	3.30	2.50	3.36	3.37
C18:1 <i>cis</i> 9	5.29	7.22	5.46	7.21	6.49
C18:2 (<i>cis</i> 9, 12)	17.21	23.47	17.63	23.43	21.30
C18:3 (<i>cis</i> 9, 12, 15)	67.45	55.36	66.25	55.58	59.17
SFA	9.32	12.74	9.81	12.59	11.94
MUFA	6.05	8.13	6.31	8.13	7.43
PUFA	84.63	79.13	83.89	79.28	81.06
UFA	90.68	87.26	90.19	87.41	88.49
n-6/n-3	0.26	0.42	0.27	0.42	0.36
UFA/SFA	9.73	6.85	9.20	6.94	8.38

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18 **Table 3.** TAG molecular species composition (%) of oil extracted from LOCS and HOCS by
 19 PLE (60°C) and SFE (CO₂ flow rate: 40 g/min; extraction time: 240 min). CN (Carbon number).
 20 D:M (dichloromethane:methanol 2:1, v/v). EtOH (ethanol).

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	Extraction	Operational conditions	TAG molecular species (%)			
			<CN50	CN50	CN52	CN54
LOCS	PLE	D:M	7.9	6.7	37.0	48.4
		EtOH	7.6	6.3	37.8	48.3
	SFE	25 MPa 40°C	3.8	6.0	38.3	51.8
		25 MPa 60°C	3.7	6.6	37.5	52.2
		45 MPa 40°C	5.2	5.9	35.2	53.7
		45 MPa 60°C	3.9	6.4	35.7	54.0
HOCS	PLE	D:M	5.0	5.2	35.1	54.7
		EtOH	6.0	4.9	34.5	54.6
	SFE	45 MPa 40°C	5.0	3.9	28.3	62.9

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